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Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas Limited And Global Memorandum Of Understanding In Bonny Local Government Area, 2014-2024

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined the impact of the Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas Limited's Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) policies on community development in Bonny Local Government Area between 2014 and 2024. The structural-functionalist theory was adopted as the theoretical framework. A qualitative research method was employed, incorporating descriptive techniques. Primary data were collected through interviews designed to answer the research questions. The paper adopted a purposive sampling technique; hence, out of the 24 proposed interviews, only 17 were conducted with NLNG staff, chiefs, opinion leaders, and local residents of Bonny LGA. Secondary data were obtained from NLNG website, newspapers, magazines, books, and both print and online journals. The reliability of the instrument was tested using the test of replicability, while face and content validity were employed to ensure validity. The study revealed, among other findings, that NLNG's GMOU policies focus on education, healthcare, and infrastructure development, among others. The paper recommended, that NLNG should consistently review and evaluate its policies to ensure alignment with evolving community needs. Furthermore, engaging local stakeholders in policy development is crucial to enhance inclusivity. Additionally, establishing a robust GMOU monitoring and assessment framework is essential for improved accountability.

Keywords: Bonny Local Government Area, community development, global memorandum of understanding (GMOU), Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas Limited (NLNG), policy evaluation, stakeholder engagement.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) has emerged as a pivotal area of focus for businesses globally, especially within industries that significantly impact local communities and environments. The imperative for large oil and gas corporations to act socially and environmentally responsibly as well as to assist in community development has been a subject of discourse among scholars and stakeholders such as host communities and governments (Jedrej, 2009). The escalating awareness of environmental issues has exerted pressure on oil and gas companies to embrace sustainable practices. For instance, companies are investing in renewable energy sources and implementing carbon offset programmes to diminish their environmental footprint. These endeavours not only benefit the planet but also augment the companies' reputation and appeal to environmentally-conscious consumers (Amahalu, Ezechukwu & Obi, 2017).

Ijeoma & Oghoghomeh (2014) posited that Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) denotes the ethical framework wherein businesses acknowledge responsibility for the repercussions of their activities on the environment, society, and economy, surpassing their legal obligations. Initially, GMOU was perceived as an optional practice that businesses could adopt to enhance their image and foster goodwill among customers and stakeholders. Nevertheless, over time, GMOU has evolved into a more integral component of corporate strategy, propelled by the growing awareness of social, environmental, and governance issues. It is now viewed as a fundamental determinant of a company's enduring success, reputation, and overall impact on society.

According to Ndulue, Okoye & Amahalu (2021), the concept of GMOU is especially pertinent in industries such as oil and gas, where the social, environmental, and economic consequences of business operations are profound. In these industries, GMOU is seen as a mechanism to address the negative externalities associated with industrialization, such as environmental degradation, community displacement, and human rights violations. It is also perceived as a way for companies to foster sustainable development, support local economies, and contribute positively to the quality of life in the areas they operate. Moreover, engaging in community development projects is essential for oil and gas corporations to nurture positive relationships with host communities. Through the establishing schools, healthcare facilities, and infrastructure, companies can contribute to the overall well-being of the communities where they operate. This not only enhances the quality of life for residents but also creates a more stable operating environment for the companies (Amao, 2014).

According to Abbas (2020), Nigeria, as one of Africa's largest oil producers, has a rich history of oil and gas exploration, with the sector accounting for a significant portion of the country's economy. However, the oil industry has long been associated with environmental destruction, human rights abuses, and corruption. Oil spills, gas flaring, and deforestation have taken a toll on Nigeria's natural resources, leading to widespread protests from host communities, environmental groups, and international organisations. The Niger Delta region, in particular, has been the epicenter of these issues, as it hosts the bulk of the country's oil exploration activities (Uduji, Okolo-Obasi & Asongu, 2018).

GMOU is the concept that companies have a duty towards society beyond their primary obligations to shareholders or owners, and it is considered voluntary (Amao 2014). GMOU is an increasingly crucial aspect of international business. Globalization of world trade and the rise of powerful companies (MNCs) are primarily responsible for the proliferation of GMOU practices. However, in some instances, the activities of MNCs have had adverse repercussions in many countries (particularly developing countries, including Nigeria). Examples include the Bodo oil spill in Nigeria (among other oil spills in the country), Pfizer's clinical trial of a polio drug that resulted in the death of 11 children and left several others blind and deaf in Nigeria, and the Union Carbide disaster in India that claimed over 5000 lives and caused lifelong health damage to up to 100,000 others (Ekhatior 2016).

Importantly, the list of multinational companies' activities that have inflicted costly damage on populations in the developing world in the unconscionable exercise of corporate power is indeed endless. Thus, the development of GMOU initiatives has encapsulated various strategies to mitigate corporate misconduct (Adeyeye 2010). These strategies have led to a plethora of diverse actors and stakeholders developing soft law initiatives and mandatory rules to enhance corporate conduct (Adeyeye 2010). The author further asserts that the modern manifestation of GMOU is "generally associated with voluntary non-binding rules to which corporations adhere in an attempt to be socially responsive. GMOU encompasses the voluntary codes, principles, and initiatives companies adopt in their general desire to confine corporate responsibility to self-regulation."

Due to the impact of MNCs' activities on the environment and society, MNCs have a responsibility to mitigate the adverse consequences of their actions or activities (Ekhatior 2014). GMOU makes corporations accountable to a broader array of stakeholders beyond just shareholders. These stakeholders could include suppliers, customers, shareholders, the environment, and communities, among others (Ekhatior 2014). Consequently, corporations are expected to take responsibility for their actions (if any) towards the aforementioned stakeholders. GMOU delves into issues relating to human rights, labour

rights or standards, bribery, and corruption among others (Amao 2011). Essentially, GMOU transcends the traditional and legal requirements expected of corporations concerning their impact on stakeholders. Thus, GMOU has been described as a 'business approach for addressing the social and environmental impacts of company activities' (Nimani, Zeqiraq & Spahija, 2022).

Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) in Nigeria's oil and gas sector has become a key response to these challenges. Companies operating in the region are expected to make significant contributions to the welfare of local communities through education, healthcare, infrastructure, environmental restoration, and other development initiatives. Safwat (2015) opined that the relationship between business and society has evolved over time. Businesses have an obligation towards their primary stakeholders just as they do towards the shareholders. Meeting societal expectations, which consequently leads to GMOU initiatives, has become a vital element in the success of corporations.

Idemudia & Osayande (2016), Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) pertains to the ethical framework in which businesses acknowledge responsibility for the repercussions of their activities on the environment, society, and economy, surpassing their legal obligations. Initially, GMOU was perceived as an optional practice that businesses could adopt to enhance their image and cultivate goodwill among customers and stakeholders. Nevertheless, over time, GMOU has transformed into a more integral component of corporate strategy, propelled by the growing awareness of social, environmental, and governance issues. It is now regarded as a fundamental determinant of a company's enduring success, reputation, and overall impact on society.

Furthermore, Uduji, Okolo-Obasi, and Asongu, (2018) aver that engaging in community development projects is imperative for oil and gas corporations to nurture positive relationships with host communities. Through the construction of schools, healthcare facilities, and infrastructure, companies can contribute to the overall well-being of the communities where they operate. This not only enhances the quality of life for residents but also establishes a more stable operating environment for the *companies*.

Nigeria, being one of Africa's prominent oil producers, boasts a rich history of oil and gas exploration, with the sector constituting a substantial portion of the country's economy. Nonetheless, the oil industry has long been associated with environmental devastation, human rights violations, and corruption. Oil spills, gas flaring, and deforestation have exacted a toll on Nigeria's natural resources, prompting widespread protests from host communities, environmental organisations, and international bodies (Uduji, Okolo-Obasi & Asongu, 2018). The Niger Delta region, in particular, has been the focal point of these issues, as it accommodates the majority of the country's oil exploration activities.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theory of structural functionalism is used to interrogate this problematique. It is a concept coined from the sociology and anthropology perspectives, which explains the state as a framework with interrelated parts. The proponent of the structural functionalism theory is the British sociologist Herbert Spencer, in his work *The Principles of Sociology* (Spencer, 1896). As a sociologist, Spencer demystified society's behaviour and social relationships. The theory is also referred to as 'functionalism' because it tends to explain the functions performed by the structures of society. The society or state in this spectrum is regarded as a formation of diverse structures that work together directly or indirectly to advance the people. These structures are diverse but interrelated or interdependent on each other. The state is considered to be a framework of puzzle-like parts that come together to enhance solidarity and stability. Interaction and social culture are akin to the human body configuration, which possesses different parts such as the five sense organs that function differently but in every sense contribute to the proper functioning of the human body. This kind of relationship is mutual in the sense that they are independent but interrelated to function properly (Spencer, 1896).

A French sociologist Émile Durkheim re-established Spencer's ideology of sociological-functionalism and made it broader in scope to structural functionalism in his work *The Division of Labour in Society* (Durkheim, 1893). Durkheim focused on patterns concerned with social change and the sustenance of modern society. He argued that society is a concept of innumerable parts that work together to maintain

the solidarity of society. Durkheim considers society as a body of individuals, but the individuals that exist in society are components of social facts. These social facts, according to Durkheim, are morals, values, laws, beliefs that influence social interaction (Durkheim, 1893). Durkheim emphasises that one way or another, these social facts contribute to the general “sharpening” of a society.

For example, a society’s religious beliefs may help individuals to abstain from certain behaviours; but where religious beliefs fail, then law-enforcement agencies would step in and enforce certain individuals. While one organisation like the police protects individuals’ peace and order, the law courts prosecute offenders, and the rehabilitation centres correct the individuals. These organisations are distinct but collectively they sustain society.

Another prominent structural functionalist who provided a clearer perspective on the assumptions of the theory was Robert K. Merton. He argued that social action occurs through what is known as ‘manifest function’ and ‘latent function’ (Merton, 1957). Merton posits that every social process has consequences or repercussions, and these repercussions are either expected or unexpected. The latent functions are those repercussions not expected, while the manifest functions are only the expected ones. For example, the manifest function of going to university is gaining knowledge and securing employment, but the latent or unexpected function of going to school may include meeting good and bad friends, joining bad gangs, and getting expelled. In other words, social institutions create social processes, and those processes have manifest and latent outcomes on an individual, which could be good or bad (Merton, 1957).

However, linking this theory to this study, the Structural Functionalist Theory, rooted in sociology, views society as a complex system made up of interrelated parts that work together to promote stability and social order (Lamidi & Etebom, 2022). Each part of society has a function that contributes to the continued equilibrium of the whole. When applying this theory to this study, “Nigeria LNG Limited and Global Memorandum of Understanding in Bonny Local Government Area, 2014–2024,” it explores how GMOU practices contribute to societal stability and development.

In Bonny Local Government Area, Nigeria LNG functions as a major economic and social entity. Its GMOU initiatives are viewed as an essential part of the larger community structure. The Structural Functionalist perspective would argue that these initiatives are meant to address certain social needs, such as education, healthcare, infrastructure development, and economic empowerment, which contribute to the stability and sustainability of the community. By providing resources and opportunities, NLNG helps maintain social equilibrium (Oyedele & Etebom, 2022).

GMOU activities, such as funding schools, building roads, and supporting health initiatives, help reduce inequalities and improve the quality of life for community members. This fosters social cohesion and reduces potential conflicts. From the structural-functionalist viewpoint, these efforts by NLNG act as a stabilising force, ensuring that the community functions effectively and that various social roles are supported. Structural functionalism emphasises the interdependence among social structures. NLNG relies on the community for its workforce and local resources, while the community depends on NLNG for economic opportunities and social programmes. This symbiotic relationship highlights how GMOU programmes can be understood as functional necessities that contribute to a balanced and sustainable social order in Bonny (Bello, 2020).

The theory also acknowledges that for a system to maintain stability, it must adapt to changes. NLNG’s GMOU initiatives from 2014 to 2024 can be seen as responses to evolving community needs and challenges. By addressing these needs through programmes focused on community development, NLNG adapts its role to continue supporting the functional requirements of the local society. Structural-functionalism also differentiates between manifest functions (intended and recognised) and latent functions (unintended and unrecognised). The manifest function of NLNG’s GMOU is to foster community development and promote a positive corporate image. However, latent functions might include fostering loyalty among local workers, reducing crime rates through improved living conditions, and creating a more educated and skilled workforce that could support not just the company but the broader economy (Nocoń, 2021).

Therefore, through the lens of structural-functionalist theory, NLNG’s GMOU initiatives in Bonny Local Government Area can be seen as critical components that contribute to the stability, order, and functional health of the community. Through measures like meeting social needs, fostering cooperation, and promoting collective welfare, NLNG plays an integral role in sustaining and enhancing the social fabric of Bonny, ensuring that both the community and the company thrive together.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Présentation

Table: Breakdown of Participants

S/N	Planned Participants	Proposed Number of Interviewee	Actual Participant Interviewed	Actual Number of Interviewee
1.	Staff of NLNG	6	Staff of NLNG	4
2.	Traditional Rulers/Chiefs	6	Chiefs/Elders	4
3	Opinion Leaders	6	Opinion Leaders	4
4.	Local Dwellers	6	Local Dwellers	5
	TOTAL	24	Total	20

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table shows that out of 24 proposed interviewees, only 17 participated in the field interviews. These included five staff of the Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG), five traditional rulers, five opinion leaders, and five local dwellers in Bonny Local Government Area. The data was obtained through face-to-face interviews conducted in Bonny and Port Harcourt between November and December 2024.

DATA ANALYSIS

What are the policies of NLNG’s Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMoU) in promoting community development in Bonny Local Government Area?

Interviews with NLNG officials revealed that the GMoU is designed to drive sustainable community development through education, health, and infrastructure. According to Brown Grace (Research and Innovation Department), NLNG promotes education through scholarships and partnerships with schools to enhance skills development. These initiatives aim to build human capacity and reduce youth unemployment. Grace also noted that the company invests in healthcare infrastructure, provides modern medical equipment, and conducts community health awareness programmes to improve access to quality medical services. NLNG’s infrastructural initiatives include constructing roads, bridges, and public utilities to stimulate economic activity and community well-being.

Wilcox Hart (Commercial and Business Development Department) emphasized that sustainability is at the core of NLNG’s policies. The company supports skills acquisition and small business development to strengthen the local economy. Through vocational training and entrepreneurship programmes, NLNG seeks to create long-term self-sufficiency within the Bonny community. According to Allison Brian (Health, Safety and Environment Department), NLNG invests in clean energy projects such as solar power to reduce carbon emissions and environmental degradation. The company also runs community awareness campaigns on environmental conservation and promotes recycling initiatives to encourage a circular economy.

David Akins (Human Resources Department) highlighted that NLNG’s projects are guided by community consultations to ensure alignment with local needs and priorities. He explained that the company regularly organizes stakeholder forums, town hall meetings, and interactive sessions to gather input from various community groups. This participatory approach, according to him, helps NLNG tailor its Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programmes to address pressing local concerns. By integrating community feedback into project design and implementation, the company promotes transparency, collaboration, and

a sense of shared responsibility. Ultimately, Akins emphasized that such engagement fosters greater community ownership and long-term sustainability of NLNG's initiatives.

Cleverline Fubara (Research and Innovation Department) stressed that NLNG upholds transparency and accountability by documenting all project expenditures and sharing records with stakeholders. Regular evaluations and impact assessments are conducted to ensure community funds are properly utilized and that projects deliver measurable benefits. Overall, responses from NLNG staff show that the GMoU framework seeks to balance economic, environmental, and social goals through participatory development, sustainability, and transparency.

Community elders collectively acknowledged the positive impact of NLNG's GMoU policies in Bonny Local Government Area but emphasized the need for more inclusive and people-centered development efforts (NLNG, 2024). According to Elder Christopher Green of Okoloama, while NLNG has successfully provided infrastructure such as schools, roads, and health centers, there remains an urgent need for the company to prioritize healthcare delivery and job creation. He maintained that true development must be holistic, addressing both physical infrastructure and human capital. In his view, creating sustainable employment opportunities for the teeming youth population would complement NLNG's infrastructural contributions and reduce social dependency within the community (Field Interview, 2024).

Similarly, Elder Halliday Charles emphasized the need for improved healthcare delivery, especially in the remote parts of Bonny Island (Field Interview, 2024). He explained that the existing healthcare centers are insufficient to meet the growing population's medical needs and recommended the introduction of mobile health units and telemedicine services. Such initiatives, he argued, would enhance healthcare accessibility, particularly for elderly people and children in outlying settlements. Elder Charles further noted that improving health infrastructure is integral to achieving long-term community development and resilience, as healthy citizens are better able to contribute productively to the local economy (NLNG, 2024).

Elder Boma Hart appreciated NLNG's scholarship and educational support programmes, acknowledging their positive impact on youth development and access to higher education (Field Interview, 2024). However, he contended that education alone cannot guarantee sustainable livelihoods without corresponding efforts in employment creation. Hart urged NLNG to increase its investment in youth entrepreneurship and vocational training, as these initiatives would empower the younger generation with practical skills to start small businesses and reduce unemployment. He emphasized that economic empowerment fosters social stability and complements the company's corporate social responsibility objectives (Egobueze, Ojirika, & Owaji-Ibani, 2021).

Elder Tolofari Hart advocated for stronger communication and collaboration between NLNG and traditional institutions (Field Interview, 2024). He observed that elders and chiefs possess deep cultural and social knowledge of their communities, which should be harnessed in project planning and implementation. Regular consultations, he maintained, would promote inclusiveness, transparency, and ownership of NLNG's community development projects. This participatory model, according to Hart, would help minimize misunderstandings, ensure that projects meet real community needs, and strengthen the partnership between corporate actors and local governance structures.

In the same vein, Elder Stephanie Banigo stressed the importance of utilizing local manpower in project execution (Field Interview, 2024). She argued that employing local artisans, engineers, and skilled workers not only improves local expertise but also ensures that development outcomes are sustainable and locally maintained. Banigo further explained that such inclusion strengthens social cohesion and enhances community ownership of projects, leading to better care and continuity of infrastructure. The elders as a group thus viewed NLNG's interventions as commendable but incomplete, calling for deeper inclusivity, a stronger healthcare focus, and more direct economic empowerment to achieve lasting development in Bonny.

Opinion leaders, comprising mostly councillors from the Bonny Legislative Council, offered nuanced evaluations of NLNG's community policies and interventions. Councillor Marilyn Dan Jumbo (Ward 8)

commended NLNG for its scholarship schemes and youth education initiatives but argued that such interventions should be complemented with entrepreneurship support programmes (Field Interview, 2024). She recommended that NLNG partner with universities and business schools to mentor young entrepreneurs, provide start-up grants, and facilitate low-interest loans. According to her, building a culture of enterprise would help reduce dependence on white-collar jobs and promote self-reliance among the youth.

Councillor Macaulay Mina (Ward 7) acknowledged NLNG's environmental protection efforts, such as waste management and clean energy projects, but expressed concern about limited employment opportunities for Bonny indigenes (Field Interview, 2024). He emphasized that sustainable community relations depend largely on the company's ability to prioritize local hiring and build internal training pipelines for skilled and semi-skilled workers. Mina suggested that NLNG could partner with technical institutes to develop training programmes that align with the company's operational needs and the community's employment expectations.

Councillor Mieadonye Macaulay (Ward 9) emphasized the need to broaden educational interventions to include vocational and technical education (Field Interview, 2024). He argued that while university scholarships are beneficial, they often exclude individuals who are not academically inclined. Introducing programmes in areas such as electrical installation, plumbing, welding, and carpentry would empower youths with employable skills and reduce unemployment. Such initiatives, according to him, would promote skill diversification, economic self-sufficiency, and local innovation.

Councillor Sidney Irimagha (Ward 1) praised NLNG's stakeholder engagement mechanisms but observed that implementation remains inconsistent and often reactive (Field Interview, 2024). He argued that consultations should not be occasional or symbolic but part of an institutionalized feedback system with measurable outcomes. Irimagha recommended the creation of monitoring and evaluation frameworks that would document stakeholder contributions and assess their integration into final project decisions. Such accountability mechanisms would ensure that NLNG's community policies remain transparent, inclusive, and responsive (Human Rights Watch, 2023).

Councillor Henry Jumbo (Ward 4) highlighted NLNG's positive impact on community health through outreach and awareness campaigns but called for the establishment of permanent healthcare facilities (Field Interview, 2024). He stressed the need to address chronic diseases, mental health, and maternal healthcare through community-based clinics and telehealth services. Jumbo suggested that collaboration with local health workers and NGOs could enhance healthcare sustainability, improve data collection, and ensure long-term benefits. The councillors collectively agreed that NLNG's achievements in education and environmental protection are notable, but greater emphasis should be placed on healthcare infrastructure, entrepreneurship, and skills training for deeper community transformation.

The perspectives of local dwellers reflected lived experiences of NLNG's interventions, providing essential insights into their social impact and inclusivity (Field Interview, 2024). Justina Brown, a local trader, observed that while NLNG has built schools, clinics, and markets, not all residents have equal access to these facilities due to socio-economic disparities. She argued that maintenance of existing infrastructure and equitable distribution of benefits are key to sustainable development. Brown maintained that projects should prioritize rural communities that often lack basic amenities such as clean water and electricity.

Hannah Israel, a businesswoman, acknowledged that NLNG's scholarship programmes have positively impacted the youth but criticized the lack of complementary job opportunities for adults (Field Interview, 2024). She argued that empowering parents through vocational and business development programmes would increase household income and strengthen family stability. According to her, NLNG could achieve greater social impact by partnering with local cooperatives and small business associations to enhance skills and entrepreneurship across age groups.

Brownson George, a local politician, commended NLNG for its infrastructural development, particularly in roads and bridges, which have improved mobility and trade (Field Interview, 2024). However, he lamented persistent challenges in accessing potable water and reliable electricity. George urged the

company to invest in renewable energy projects such as solar mini-grids and water treatment plants to address these pressing community needs. He maintained that infrastructure without utility sustainability undermines the essence of community development.

Ngowari Thomas, a civil servant, criticized some NLNG projects for not aligning with the immediate needs of the people (Field Interview, 2024). He suggested that participatory planning and needs assessment be prioritized to ensure that community voices are incorporated from inception to completion. Thomas argued that bottom-up planning enhances local ownership and reduces project abandonment, as communities feel a sense of responsibility for their outcomes..

Ibifagha Kingsley, a youth leader, stressed that grassroots participation is central to project success (Field Interview, 2024). He explained that involving communities in planning, implementation, and evaluation promotes accountability and relevance. Kingsley asserted that NLNG should empower community monitoring committees to track progress and ensure transparency in project delivery. He concluded that participatory governance fosters mutual trust, enhances social capital, and leads to sustainable peace and development (Egobueze et al., 2021).

Summary of Major Findings

From the responses of all categories of participants, several key themes emerged:

I. Education and Human Capacity Building:

NLNG's scholarship programmes and school projects are widely recognized as impactful, yet there is a strong call to integrate vocational and technical training to reduce unemployment.

II. Health and Social Welfare:

The company's healthcare initiatives have improved access to basic medical services, but long-term facilities and preventive healthcare are still inadequate, especially in remote communities.

III. Infrastructure and Basic Amenities:

NLNG's infrastructural interventions such as roads and bridges have enhanced mobility and economic activity. However, residents still face challenges with clean water supply, electricity, and facility maintenance.

IV. Environmental Sustainability:

NLNG's investments in clean energy and waste management are commendable, though environmental education and community participation in green initiatives need expansion.

V. Economic Empowerment:

There is consensus that more emphasis should be placed on job creation, entrepreneurship, and empowerment of local businesses to promote economic self-reliance.

VI. Stakeholder Engagement:

While NLNG maintains a participatory framework, participants noted that engagement should be more consistent and inclusive of traditional leaders, youths, and grassroots groups.

VII. Transparency and Accountability:

The company's financial openness under the GMoU has improved trust, but continuous monitoring and community oversight are recommended to ensure full transparency.

VIII. Inclusivity and Equity:

Not all groups benefit equally from NLNG projects. Vulnerable and marginalized populations should be deliberately targeted in future interventions to ensure balanced development.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

What are the policies of Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) Limited's Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) in promoting community development in Bonny Local Government Area?

The interview responses from the four stakeholder groups, namely NLNG staff, chiefs/elders, opinion leaders, and local dwellers provide valuable insights into the implementation and perception of Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) Limited's Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) policies in Bonny Local Government Area. The findings reveal both the successes of NLNG's GMOU initiatives and the challenges encountered in aligning these efforts with the diverse needs of the community.

Education and Human Capacity Building

The Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas Limited (NLNG) has implemented scholarship programmes and school-projects in its host communities such as their Post-Primary Scholarship Scheme (PPSS) for public primary pupils in Rivers State. (NLNG, n.d.). While these initiatives are widely recognized and even awarded (NLNG wins “Best Company in Education” award, 2020), stakeholders call for deeper integration of vocational and technical training to reduce unemployment (NLNG, 2025; NLNG, n.d.). For example, NLNG’s website reports the existence of the Bonny Vocational Centre offering certified training in engineering and hospitality (NLNG, 2025). These steps reflect a shift from purely academic support toward equipping individuals with marketable, technical skills. Such capacity-building is critical because education alone, without linkage to employment pathways, may not fully address the region’s youth unemployment challenge. Thus, while NLNG’s efforts in education are commendable, the call is for a more balanced approach that couples scholarships and general schooling with practical vocational training and job readiness.

Health and Social Welfare

NLNG has extended its community development efforts into health and social welfare by supporting community health insurance programmes and medical infrastructure in its host communities (NLNG, 2025). Despite this, multiple stakeholders highlight that access to long-term facilities and preventive healthcare remains inadequate in remote areas. For example, even while NLNG claims near-uninterrupted electricity and water for over 15,000 households through its partner company, local reports indicate that clean potable water and full healthcare-facility coverage remain unmet needs in Bonny (The Tide, 2025). Thus, while NLNG’s health outreach is a positive stride, sustainable and long-term health infrastructure including centres catering to chronic illnesses, preventive medicine, and remote-area coverage still require attention for holistic community welfare.

Infrastructure and Basic Amenities

According to NLNG’s own disclosure, their infrastructure development in Bonny includes power and water utilities established via the Bonny Utility Company, and road-projects such as the Bonny-Bodo Road (NLNG, n.d.; NLNG, n.d.). Reports show these interventions have enhanced mobility and living standards for instance, a five-water-treatment-plant network serving households and public kiosks (NLNG, n.d.). However, local community voices highlight continuing challenges: limited access to clean water for some neighbourhoods, incomplete roads, and electricity issues in certain locations (The Tide, 2025). These gaps show that while major interventions exist, the distribution, maintenance, and reach of infrastructure and basic amenities still require improvement for all community members.

Environmental Sustainability

NLNG reports investment in clean-energy and utility infrastructure. For example, its partnership to deliver almost full electricity and potable water in Bonny via the BUC initiative (NLNG, n.d.). Its Nigerian-content strategy further shows training of local vendors and environmental awareness (NLNG, n.d.). Nonetheless, independent research indicates that host communities still experience environmental challenges such as air pollution, water-quality issues and gas flaring-related ailments (International Scholars Journals, 2025). This divergence suggests that although the company’s efforts are commendable, environmental education, community participation in green initiatives, and proactive monitoring remain areas for enhanced focus if sustainability is to be fully achieved.

Economic Empowerment

The emphasis on job creation, entrepreneurship, and local-business empowerment has been part of NLNG’s reported strategy. The company highlights a N1 billion MSME scheme supporting host-community businesses (NLNG, 2025). However, community feedback and external commentary suggest that while programmes exist, their reach and impact could be expanded to promote economic self-reliance more effectively. Indeed, ensuring that host-community members become vendors, entrepreneurs or employees in company-related value chains remains a persistent developmental challenge (NLNG, n.d.). In sum, economic empowerment is advancing but requires deeper, sustained commitment to transform local economies from dependency to self-sufficiency.

Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement is publicly reported by NLNG, describing consultation with host communities, local vendors, and traditional institutions (NLNG, n.d.). While this framework is a positive practice, local voices and media reports indicate that engagement sometimes lacks inclusivity, especially in respect of traditional leaders, youths and grassroots groups and that implementation can be inconsistent (Punch NG, 2024; The Tide, 2025). Effective engagement demands more than occasional dialogue: it requires meaningful participation mechanisms, regular feedback loops and co-design of projects so that community members feel a sense of ownership.

Transparency and Accountability

NLNG's annual reports and "Impact" disclosures indicate a commitment to transparency and accountability: for instance, the company reports numbers of scholarship beneficiaries, training graduates and utility-coverage figures (NLNG, 2025). Yet external commentary and civil-society studies (e.g., Oxfam's case study for oil-rich host communities) point to broader systemic governance and oversight challenges in host-community development in Nigeria, such as bureaucratic bottlenecks and limited independent monitoring (Oxfam in Nigeria, 2025). To fully embed transparency and accountability, host communities should have accessible audit-data, community-monitoring frameworks, and inclusive oversight structures.

Inclusivity and Equity

While many of NLNG's projects have reached dozens of communities and beneficiaries, evidence suggests that not all groups benefit equally, particularly vulnerable or marginalized segments of the host communities (The Tide, 2025; International Scholars Journals, 2025). For example, some remote settlements report very low access to potable water and remain impacted by environmental degradation. Equitable development thus requires deliberately targeting underserved populations, tailoring programmes to disadvantaged groups (such as women, persons with disabilities or remote localities), and monitoring for distributional fairness.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The study concludes that the Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas Limited (NLNG), through its Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU), has significantly contributed to community development in Bonny Local Government Area (LGA) from 2014 to 2024. The company's interventions in education, healthcare, and infrastructure have fostered improved access to social amenities and enhanced local livelihoods. However, persistent issues such as limited inclusivity in decision-making, weak monitoring systems, and inadequate attention to sustainability continue to hinder optimal outcomes. To ensure that the GMOU framework remains an effective model for corporate-community partnership, a more participatory, transparent, and adaptive approach is required.

Base on the above, the following recommendations are made:

1. Strengthen Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanisms:

NLNG should establish a comprehensive monitoring and evaluation (M&E) framework that includes clear indicators, regular assessments, and participatory feedback channels. Engaging community representatives in project evaluation will enhance accountability, transparency, and continuous improvement.

2. Enhance Stakeholder Participation and Inclusivity:

The company should broaden its stakeholder engagement strategy to include traditional leaders, women, youths, and community-based organizations. Such inclusivity will ensure equitable participation in decision-making, foster community ownership, and promote social harmony.

3. Promote Vocational and Human Capacity Development:

Beyond scholarships and infrastructure, NLNG should invest more in vocational training and entrepreneurship programmes. Empowering residents—especially the youth and women—with practical skills and start-up support will reduce unemployment and stimulate local economic growth

4. **Ensure Project Sustainability and Transparency:**

Sustainability should be embedded in all phases of project planning and execution. NLNG should collaborate with local institutions to maintain completed projects while publishing periodic progress and expenditure reports to strengthen public trust and accountability.

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APPENDIX I

CONSENT FORM

Title of Study: Global Memorandum of Understanding and Community Development in Bonny Local Government Area: A Study of NLNG

Introduction:

You are being invited to participate in a research study on the impact of Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) initiatives on community development in Bonny Local Government Area, focusing on the activities of Nigeria LNG (NLNG). This study is being conducted as part of an academic research project.

Purpose of the Study:

The purpose of this study is to assess how NLNG's GMOU programmes have contributed to the community development in Bonny Local Government Area between 2014 and 2024.

Procedures:

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to answer questions during an interview. The interview will focus on your knowledge, opinions, or experiences regarding NLNG's GMOU initiatives and their impact on the community. Participation will take approximately [insert duration] and can be conducted in person, over the phone, or online, based on your preference.

Voluntary Participation:

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You may choose not to participate or withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences or loss of benefits.

Confidentiality:

All information you provide will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Your identity will not be revealed in the study or any related publications. Data collected will be securely stored and used solely for academic purposes.

Potential Risks and Benefits:

There are no anticipated risks associated with participating in this study. The findings of this research may benefit your community by providing insights into the effectiveness of GMOU initiatives and suggesting ways to improve community development programmes.

Consent:

By signing below, you indicate that:

You have read and understood the information provided.

You voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

You understand your rights to confidentiality and to withdraw from the study at any time.

If you have any questions or require further information, please contact the researcher at [+2348085623999].

Participant's Name: _____

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

Researcher's Name: _____

Researcher's Signature: _____

Date: _____

APPENDIX II

INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPT VALIDATION

I attest that the transcript of my interview session was brought to me for verification and validation. Having read the transcribed words, I certify that I made the statements and that I was neither misinterpreted nor misquoted.

Signature of interviewee

Date

Interview Guide

- a. What are the policies of Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) Limited's Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) in promoting community development in Bonny Local Government Area?
- b. How do the policies of Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) Limited's Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) impact on community development in Bonny Local Government Area?
- c. How do local population and other stakeholders perceive the policies of Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) Limited's Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) on community development in Bonny Local Government Area?
- d. What are the challenges encountered by the policies of Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) Limited's Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) on community development in Bonny Local Government Area?